

IPBES VA Chapter 2 - Behaviour theories literature review / IPBES Values assessment (2.7)

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Description

This review corresponds to the IPBES values assessment. Chapter 2 experts found that reports about behaviour did not always reflect values (known as the value-action gap). Thus, it was considered important to identify how values and behaviour are connected. In order to do so, a meta-review was conducted, using existing reviews of behaviour theories to develop both the list of theories to be used for the analysis,

but also, to obtain information about these theories. Experts focused on theories of human behaviour in general (rather than pro-environmental behaviour specifically) in order to include a much wider realm of scholarly research. This behaviour theories literature review was conducted as part of the stage 2 of the literature review strategy for the chapter. Chapter 2's stage 2 is a way to incorporate multiple sources of evidence appropriate for each section and subsection, with searches tailored to specific questions that permit to obtain a broader and deeper database to fulfil the mandate of the scoping document.

Process overview

Protocol

Based on expert-knowledge, two sources were identified as relevant to carry this review: Mitchie et al., 2014 and Kwon & Silva, 2020. Each of these sources compiles a list of behaviour theories that were created and refined in different ways, and thus, the two lists are highly complementary and include a variety of behaviour theories deemed to be important across a wide array of contexts. The combination of the lists of the two sources can be found in **(A)**. Theories found in both sources were kept as a single entry.

Type of analysis/search/review: Meta-review of behaviour theories listed in Mitchie et al. 2014 and Kwon & Silva, 2019.

- **Sample extracted:** 134 theories
- **Fields extracted (A):**
 - **Name of the theory**
 - **Full reference**
 - **Source**
- **Location and format of the data (A):** IPBES_VA_2.7_07-2020_(A).csv

Treatment applied: Experts identified constructs in the behaviour theories. The process to identify constructs is described in **(R1)**. The final list of constructs identified is composed of 2232 constructs found in **(B)**.

- **Sample extracted:** 2232 constructs
- **Fields extracted (B):**
 - **Source**
 - **Theory name**
 - **Constructs**
- **Location and format of the data (B):** IPBES_VA_2.7_06-2021_(B).csv

Treatment applied: Constructs were categorised as value-related constructs or “all other constructs”. Criteria used to make this categorization are presented in **(R2)**.

Results of the analysis are presented in *section 2.4.1.2* and a further description, discussion and conclusion of the analysis can be found in **(C)**.

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_2.7_07-2020_(A)	csv	33 KB	Database with the list of 134 behaviour theories used in this review.
B	IPBES_VA_2.7_06-2021_(B)	csv	130 KB	Database with the list of 2232 constructs identified in the behaviour theories found in (A)

C	IPBES_VA_2.7_11-2020_(C)	pdf	312 KB	Report of the process of the literature review on behaviour theories, including description, discussion and conclusions of the analysis.
R1	IPBES_VA_2.7_03-2021_(R1)	pdf	93 KB	Description of the process to identify constructs in the theories listed in (A).
R2	IPBES_VA_2.7_09_2021_(R2)	pdf	138 KB	Description of the process to categorise the constructs in (B) as value related or all other constructs.